

AN IMPROVEMENT IN THE SELF-EVALUATION OF THE DIDACTIC ACTIONS DEVELOPED

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Abstract. In this article is considered methodical questions and major factors of development of formation of information competence of the teachers increasing of qualification with application of modern technology of training.

Keywords: information competence, major factors of information competence, technologies of training, active methods.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрены методические вопросы и основные факторы развития формирования информационной компетентности преподавателей повышения квалификации с применением современных технологий обучения.

Ключевые слова: Информационная компетентность, основные факторы информационной компетентности, технологии обучения, активные методы.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'qitishning zamonaviy texnologiyalarini qo'llash orqali o'qituvchilarning malakasini oshirishning axborot kompetentsiyasini shakllantirishning uslubiy masalalari va asosiy omillari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot kompetentsiyasi, axborot kompetentsiyasining asosiy omillari, o'qitish texnologiyalari, faol usullar.

Introduction

“He who possesses knowledge possesses the world”

Nathan Rothschild.

The requirements of the law, the National Program for Personnel Training and the requirements of the teacher are being expanded. In the 21st century, pedagogue required extensive knowledge, thorough practical training, high pedagogical skills, competence and creativity. In preschool, personal qualities of a leader are important. The personality traits of a leader providing a humane factor in early childhood education: rigor, honesty, honesty, kindness and courtesy. These qualities should determine the importance of the educator to the learners. The personal qualities influence the skills of teaching and training. In the book “Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility must be the daily routine of every leader's work” by President Sh. Mirziyoev cited that “Independent thinking, dedicating modern science and professions, dedication to country, his people, continuing what we started The most mature and capable leader is the one whose mission is to bring the next generation to perfection”. Indeed, in the development of socio-economic relations in the 21st century, it is becoming increasingly clear that human intelligence and spirituality are the main coordinating, developing factors and tools. That is why humanism has emerged as the basic principle of building a legal, democratic state and a free civil society based on a market economy [1].

Education in any developed society is a leading social institution that solves a whole range of important tasks related to the effective transfer of values and experience accumulated by previous generations to new generations of citizens as a basis for further development.

In conditions of transition to an information society the requirements to professional training of the teacher, in particular to a level his professional competence raise. One of major competence of the modern teacher is the information competence.

Last years the prompt penetration of mathematics and computer technologies in different spheres became the come to pass fact. In this connection there are completely new tasks and before education. It is necessary so to organize process of training, that teachers were able to apply modern technologies of training. For this purpose they should receive of knowledge from integration of employment of mathematics and computer science.

Now tasks about integration of mathematics and computer science becomes extremely urgent for maximum education - in connection with urgent activity of aspect of perfection of the contents of education, and also in view of the tendencies determined by transition to an information society. For this reason the special urgency is got with questions, in various subject domains appreciably depend on the answer on which directions of perfection of the contents of education, and first of all - mathematics and computer science.

Between subjects communication is a modern principle of training, which influences selection and structure of an educational material of a lot of subjects, strengthening system of knowledge of the teachers, makes active methods of training, focus on application of the complex forms of organization of training, providing unity of educational process and formations of information competence of the teachers.

The information competence of the teacher at the present stage, is understood, how his readiness and ability independently to use modern telecommunication technologies in pedagogical activity for the decision of a wide circle of educational tasks and to project ways of improvement of professional skill in this sphere.

Information competence of the teachers we shall understand an obligatory component of professional competence of the teacher, which defines readiness and ability it effectively to decide professional tasks, according to stages of pedagogical activity, means of modern computer technologies, in view of means and forms of information job [2].

Means of modern computer technologies we shall understand program, hardware software both means and devices functioning on the basis of computer engineering, and also modern means and systems of processing of the information, information exchange ensuring operations under the tax, accumulation, storage, processing, transfer of the information and opportunity of access to information resources of computer networks.

With the help of multilateral intersubject communications not only at a qualitatively new level the tasks of training, development and education of the students are decided, but also the base to complex vision, approach and decision of complex problems of reality is pawned. For this reason the intersubject communications are the important condition and result of the complex approach in educational process.

The purpose application intersubject communications of computer science and the mathematics in a rate improvement of professional skill are to generate at the teachers information competence, skill to transform in practice information objects with the help of means of information technologies. These as allow to show communication of subjects, learn (teach) to apply in practice theoretical knowledge, fulfill skills of job on the computer, make active pedagogical activity of the teachers, stimulate to their independent purchase of practical knowledge. In a rate improvement of professional skill each teacher works actively and keen, at the teachers the inquisitiveness and activity develops.

For formation of information competence of the teachers with application of intersubject communication of computer science and mathematics is carried out:

- integrated employment;
- decision of mathematical tasks on employment of computer science;
- study adjacent with mathematics by that;
- registration of the abstracts, performances(statements) on subjects, materials to employment.

By one of the factors promoting development of information competence of the teachers in process improvement of professional skill, the integration of disciplines "mathematics" and "computer science" acts on the basis of computer technology.

Integration as means of training should give students that knowledge, which reflects connection of separate parts of the world as systems to learn to perceive the world as a single unit, in which all elements are interconnected [3].

The mathematical methods are used in the decision of tasks for processing results of measurements, in management for a quantitative substantiation of the accepted decisions, development and automation of labour-consuming jobs. Thus from the teacher it is required to know not only mathematical methods of account used for the decision of tasks of professional activity, but also ways of their realization by means of tool computer technologies.

Conclusion

Having information competence, the teacher not only aspires to use of information technologies in the job, but also simulates and designs pedagogical technologies.

Besides the intersubject communications of computer science and mathematics are carried out at registration of the abstracts, performances on subjects. Creation of electronic presentations to employment, performances at scientifically practical conferences.

Use of applied tasks at realization of employment allows to raise not only level of mathematical preparation, but also renders influence on development of information competence of the teacher, that is a necessary condition of preparation of the competent experts for introduction of means of tool computer technologies in educational process.

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